

Photonic vaccines may change the genetic circuits and control infectious cells

Alireza Sepehri
Independent Researcher, neyshabour, Iran

Abstract: microbial waves like viral waves could be detected by eye cells, convert to electrochemical signals and transmit to the brain. Then, these waves could move along neurons and achieve to cells, nucleus and DNAs. Each DNA is formed from bases which take the shape of genetic capacitors, inductors and resistances. These electric devices are connected to each other and build some circuits similar to TV ones. Like a TV, these DNA circuits emit some waves which shoot charges towards phospholipids, ATPs and other phosphoric layers and produce some images of initial viruses. These viruses could be reverse transcribed, integrate into the DNA and change its electronic circuits. Consequently, DNA waves are changed and new waves cause to production of new products. These changes in infectious cells motivate the immune system and cause to attacks of T-cells. This technique may be used in producing new vaccines.

Keywords: Viruses; Circuits; Waves; Gene; Products; Frequencies

Introduction:

Recently, some authors have investigated the possibility that SARS-CoV-2 RNAs can be reverse-transcribed and integrated into the DNA of human cells in culture and that transcription of the integrated sequences might account for some of the positive PCR tests seen in patients. This idea may be helpful for producing the best types of vaccines. There are several types of vaccines against SARS-CoV-2 [2,3]. For example, some authors have evaluated the effect of first-dose BNT162b2 vaccination on test positivity rates and found a fourfold reduction in asymptomatic infection amongst HCWs ≥ 12 days post-vaccination. These data have provided real-world evidence of short-term protection against asymptomatic SARS-CoV-2 infection following a single dose of BNT162b2 vaccine, suggesting that mass first-dose vaccination will reduce SARS-CoV-2 transmission, as well as the burden of COVID-19 disease [4]. Another authors have reported on a phase 3 clinical trial of the mRNA-1273 vaccine against SARS-CoV-2, and they have provided information on immediate injection-site reactions, which were observed in 84.2% of the participants after the first dose. The trial also showed that delayed injection-site reactions (defined in that trial as those with an onset on or after day

8) occurred in 244 of the 30,420 participants (0.8%) after the first dose and in 68 participants (0.2%) after the second dose. These reactions included erythema, induration, and tenderness [5]. Some other authors have measured neutralizing antibody responses after the first and second immunizations using pseudoviruses that expressed the wild-type spike protein or a mutated spike protein that contained the eight amino acid changes found in the B.1.1.7 variant. The sera from individuals who received the vaccine exhibited a broad range of neutralizing titres against the wild-type pseudoviruses that were modestly reduced against the B.1.1.7 variant [6]. Another authors have shown that neutralization geometric mean titers (GMTs) of 20 BNT162b2 vaccine-elicited human sera against the three mutant viruses were 0.81- to 1.46-fold of the GMTs against parental virus, indicating small effects of these mutations on neutralization by sera elicited by two BNT162b2 doses [7]. Other group have described that the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) B.1.1.7 (VOC 202012/01) variant that emerged in late 2020 in the United Kingdom has many changes in the spike protein gene. They have shown that the vaccine remained effective against B.1.1.7 with a slight but significant decrease in neutralization that was more apparent in participants under 55 years of age [8]. Another team have reported that the viral load was substantially reduced for infections occurring 12–37 d after the first dose of BNT162b2 vaccine [9]. Another investigators have argued that numerous variants of SARS-CoV-2-harboring mutations in spike have arisen globally. They have stated that both receptor-binding domain (RBD) and non-RBD mutations mediate escape from vaccine-induced humoral immunity [10]. Another authors have introduced the safety, tolerability, and immunogenicity of a candidate COVID-19 vaccine, CoronaVac, containing inactivated SARS-CoV-2, in adults aged 60 years and older [11]. Other models have shown that the combination of different vaccine dosing regimes and variations in the robustness of natural and vaccinal immunity may result in a wide range of potential epidemiological and evolutionary outcomes in the medium term [12]. Another authors have reported that BBV152 led to tolerable safety outcomes and enhanced immune responses. Both Algel-IMDG formulations were selected for phase 2 immunogenicity trials [13]. Another researchers have discussed that the inactivated SARS-CoV-2 vaccine, BBIBP-CorV, is safe and well tolerated at all tested doses in two age groups. Humoral responses against SARS-CoV-2 were induced in all vaccine recipients on day 42 [14].

Motivated by above investigations, we design a model which considers interaction between circuits of human's DNA and transcribed SARS-CoV-2 RNA. We will describe that how viral circuits control the exchanged waves between DNAs, RNA

and proteins and affect on cellular evolutions and immune system. We also consider a new model of vaccines which are induced by electromagnetic waves.

II. Theoretical model: Induction of viral vaccines by waves and controlling productions of cells

We can describe the model in several phases:

1. Each DNA is formed from hexagonal and pentagonal bases which are located near each other and exchange waves and energies. These hexagonal/pentagonal bases could play the role of planes of capacitors. Because, they could store electrical energies like capacitors (See figure 1).
2. Each DNA is coiled several times around different axes. By each coiling, a type of an inductor is emerged which stores and emits magnetic fields (See Figure 1).
3. Bases are connected with each other by some common electrons. These electrons are confined and produce some resistances in front of exchanging charges, waves and energies (See Figure 1).
4. DNA capacitors and inductors join to each other and form several resonance circuits which each of them emits an special wave (See Figure 1).
5. These DNA circuits could exchange some currents and waves with brains. For example, when an eye sees an objects, its image converts to electro-chemical signals, transmits to the brain, moves along neurons, achieves to cells, nucleus and DNAs and converts to waves again. These new waves shoot waves towards phosphoric layers like phospholipids and ATP. Like a TV which waves shoot electrons towards a phosphoric layer and produce images, DNA waves shoot charges towards phospholipids and ATP and create images (See Figure 2).
6. If initial image be a virus, it couldn't be seen by our eyes, however, its waves could be recognized by eye cells, transmit to the brain and after to cells and produce viral images by DNA circuits within the nucleus (See Figure 2).
7. If images of virus are replicated by polymerases and some real viruses are emerged, these viruses may be reverse transcribed and produce some genes which couple to DNA genetics. In these conditions, there are two types of circuits, one related to DNA genes and other related to viral genes. Viral genes emit some new waves which cancel the effect of DNA waves. Consequently, DNAs couldn't exchange waves with RNAs and proteins and lose any control on them (See Figure 3).

8. On the other hand, new viral circuits produce some new products. These products are recognized by immune system and cause to attacks of T-cells. Thus, we can use of this technique in producing vaccines (See Figure 3).

Figure 1. An electrical circuit for a DNA

Figure 2. Induction of viral images within cells by using electromagnetic waves

Figure 3. Viral circuits are connected to DNA circuits and produce new products.

III. Mathematical model: Correlating function

In previous section, we have designed an electronic circuit for a DNA. We have shown that this circuit controls proteins, RNAs and other products. When, a virus enters into a cell, its circuit may emits some waves which cancel waves of a DNA and decrease its control on evolutions of a cell. To show this mathematically, we will obtain a correlating function between DNA circuits and products.

To begin, we use of below definitions for elements of a DNA genetic circuit.

$$C_{\text{Hexagon-pentagon}} = \epsilon A_{\text{Hexagon-pentagon}} / d_{\text{Hexagon-pentagon}}$$

$$C_{\text{Hexagon-Hexagon}} = \epsilon A_{\text{Hexagon-Hexagon}} / d_{\text{Hexagon-Hexagon}} \quad (1)$$

where $C_{\text{Hexagon-pentagon}}$, $C_{\text{Hexagon-Hexagon}}$ are hexagon-pentagon and hexagon-hexagon capacities. Also, $A_{\text{Hexagon-pentagon}}$, $A_{\text{Hexagon-Hexagon}}$ are hexagon-pentagon and hexagon-hexagon areas and $d_{\text{Hexagon-pentagon}}$, $d_{\text{Hexagon-Hexagon}}$ are separation distances between hexagonal and pentagonal manifolds. The stored energy in these capacitors could be obtained from below equations:

$$E_{\text{Capacitor-Hexagon-Hexagon}} = \frac{1}{2} C_{\text{Hexagon-Hexagon}} [V_{\text{Hexagon-Hexagon}}]^2$$

$$E_{\text{Capacitor-Hexagon-pentagon}} = \frac{1}{2} C_{\text{Hexagon-pentagon}} [V_{\text{Hexagon-pentagon}}]^2 \quad (2)$$

Where $E_{\text{Capacitor-Hexagon-Hexagon}}$, $E_{\text{Capacitor-Hexagon-pentagon}}$ are stored energies within capacitors and $V_{\text{Hexagon-Hexagon}}$, $V_{\text{Hexagon-pentagon}}$ are related voltages. These voltages could be obtained from below equations:

$$V_{\text{Hexagon-pentagon}} = V_{\text{Hexagon}} + V_{\text{pentagon}}$$

$$V_{\text{Hexagon}} = \sum k_{\text{Hexagon-i}} q_{\text{Hexagon-i}} / r_{\text{Hexagon-i}}$$

$$V_{\text{pentagon}} = \sum k_{\text{pentagon-i}} q_{\text{pentagon-i}} / r_{\text{pentagon-i}} \quad (3)$$

$$V_{\text{Hexagon-Hexagon}} = V_{\text{Hexagon}} + V'_{\text{Hexagon}}$$

$$V_{\text{Hexagon}} = \sum k_{\text{Hexagon-I}} q_{\text{Hexagon-I}} / r_{\text{Hexagon-i}}$$

$$V'_{\text{Hexagon}} = \sum k'_{\text{Hexagon-j}} q'_{\text{Hexagon-j}} / r'_{\text{Hexagon-j}} \quad (4)$$

Where $q_{\text{Hexagon-I}}$, $q_{\text{pentagon-I}}$ are charges on pentagonal/hexagonal manifolds and $r_{\text{Hexagon-i}}$, $r_{\text{pentagon-I}}$ are their distances from a test point.

For genetic resistances, we can use of below equations:

$$E_{\text{Resistance-Hexagon-pentagon}} = \frac{1}{2} R_{\text{Hexagon-pentagon}} [I_{\text{Hexagon-pentagon}}]^2$$

$$E_{\text{Resistance-Hexagon-Hexagon}} = \frac{1}{2} R_{\text{Hexagon-Hexagon}} [I_{\text{Hexagon-Hexagon}}]^2 \quad (5)$$

Where $E_{\text{Resistance-Hexagon-pentagon}}$, $E_{\text{Resistance-Hexagon-Hexagon}}$ are hexagon-hexagon and hexagon-pentagon resistance energies. These resistances have the below equations:

$$R_{\text{Hexagon-pentagon}} = \rho_{\text{Hexagon-pentagon}} l_{\text{Hexagon-pentagon}} / A_{\text{Hexagon-pentagon}}$$

$$R_{\text{Hexagon-Hexagon}} = \rho_{\text{Hexagon-Hexagon}} l_{\text{Hexagon-Hexagon}} / A_{\text{Hexagon-Hexagon}} \quad (6)$$

Where ρ_s are special resistances depending on the genus of medium, l_s are lengths of systems and A_s are their areas.

Each DNA could be coiled and produce several inductors. We can write:

$$L_{\text{Gene-coil-I}} = \mu_{\text{Gene-coil-I}} K_{\text{Gene-coil-I}} [N_{\text{Gene-coil-i}}]^2 A_{\text{Gene-coil-I}} / l_{\text{Gene-coil-I}} \quad (7)$$

where

L = inductance in henries (H)

K = Nagaoka coefficient

N = number of turns

l = length of coil in metres (m) (8)

Energy of inductors could be obtained from below equation:

$$E_{\text{Gene-coil-I}} = \frac{1}{2} L_{\text{Gene-coil-I}} [I_{\text{Gene-coil-i}}]^2 \quad (9)$$

Where $I_{\text{Gene-coil-I}}$ is the current and could be obtained from below equation:

$$I_{\text{Gene-coil-I}} = n_{\text{Gene-coil-I}} Q_{\text{Gene-coil-I}} \text{VELOCITY}_{\text{Gene-coil-i}} \quad (10)$$

Where $n_{\text{Gene-coil-I}}$ is the number of genetic charges, $Q_{\text{Gene-coil-I}}$ is the genetic charge and could be obtained from below equation:

$$Q_{\text{Gene-coil-I}} = n_{\text{gene- Gene-coil-I}} q_{\text{gene- Gene-coil-I}} \quad (11)$$

where

$$q_{\text{gene- Gene-coil-I}} = n_{\text{charge- gene- Gene-coil-I}} q_{\text{charge- gene- Gene-coil-I}}$$

where $n_{\text{charge- gene- Gene-coil-I}}$ is the number of charged atoms and electrons and $q_{\text{charge- gene- Gene-coil-I}}$ is their charge values.

Total energy of a gene could be obtained by summing over energies of all capacitors, inductors and resistances:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{\text{Gene,Tot}} = & \sum E_{\text{Capacitor-Hexagon-pentagon,I}} + \sum E_{\text{Capacitor-Hexagon-Hexagon,j}} + \\ & + \sum E_{\text{Resistance-Hexagon-pentagon,k}} + \sum E_{\text{Resistance-Hexagon-Hexagon,l}} \\ & + \sum E_{\text{Gene coil-m}} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

For this system, we can obtain the wave equations and calculate the frequencies of system. For example, for a system without resistance, we have:

Resistance $\approx 0 \rightarrow$

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_{\text{gene}} = & \left[\left[A \sum [L_{\text{Gene-coil-I}} \sin(\omega_{\text{Gene-coil-I}} t)] + B \sum [L_{\text{Gene-coil-j}} \sin(\omega_{\text{Gene-coil-j}} t)]^{-1} \right] \right. \\ & \left. D \sum [C_{\text{Gene-Hexagon-pentagon ,k}} \sin(\omega_{\text{Gene-Hexagon-pentagon ,k}} t)] + \right. \\ & \left. F \sum [C_{\text{Gene-Hexagon-Hexagon ,m}} \sin(\omega_{\text{Gene-Hexagon-Hexagon ,m}} t)] \right. \\ & \left. H \sum [C_{\text{Gene-Hexagon-pentagon ,n}} \sin(\omega_{\text{Gene-Hexagon-pentagon ,n}} t)]^{-1} + \right. \\ & \left. U \sum [C_{\text{Gene-Hexagon-Hexagon ,m}} \sin(\omega_{\text{Gene-Hexagon-Hexagon ,l}} t)]^{-1} \right]^{-1/2} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Where (A,D,F,H,U) are some parameters, ω s are frequencies which are applied by external fields, while Ω_{gene} is the resonance frequency of a gene. Above equation shows that frequency of a gene depends on the external waves and also time. By passing time, frequency of a gene changes which means type of exchanged information changes.

A virus also has its own circuit and frequency:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Omega_{\text{virus}} = & \left[\left[W \sum [L_{\text{virus-coil-I}} \sin(\omega_{\text{virus-coil-I}} t)] + T \sum [L_{\text{virus-coil-j}} \sin(\omega_{\text{virus-coil-j}} t)]^{-1} \right] \right. \\
& \left. Y [C_{\text{virus,Hexagon-pentagon},k} \sin(\omega_{\text{virus,Hexagon-pentagon},k} t)] + \right. \\
& \left. O \sum [C_{\text{virus,Hexagon-Hexagon},m} \sin(\omega_{\text{virus,Hexagon-Hexagon},m} t)] \right. \\
& \left. Z \sum [C_{\text{virus,Hexagon-pentagon},n} \sin(\omega_{\text{virus,Hexagon-pentagon},n} t)]^{-1} + \right. \\
& \left. X \sum [C_{\text{virus,Hexagon-Hexagon},l} \sin(\omega_{\text{virus,Hexagon-Hexagon},l} t)]^{-1} \right]^{-1/2} \quad (14)
\end{aligned}$$

Where (W,T,Y,O,Z,X) are some parameters, ω s are frequencies which are applied by external fields, while Ω_{virus} is the resonance frequency of a virus. If this viral circuit connects to a genetic circuit, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Omega_{\text{gene-virus}} \approx & \left[\left[A \sum [L_{\text{Gene-coil-I}} \sin(\omega_{\text{Gene-coil-I}} t)] + B \sum [L_{\text{Gene-coil-j}} \sin(\omega_{\text{Gene-coil-j}} t)]^{-1} \right] \right. \\
& \left. + 1 \right] \left[D \sum [C_{\text{Gene-Hexagon-pentagon},k} \sin(\omega_{\text{Gene-Hexagon-pentagon},k} t)] + \right. \\
& \left. F \sum [C_{\text{Gene-Hexagon-Hexagon},m} \sin(\omega_{\text{Gene-Hexagon-Hexagon},m} t)] \right. \\
& \left. H \sum [C_{\text{Gene-Hexagon-pentagon},n} \sin(\omega_{\text{Gene-Hexagon-pentagon},n} t)]^{-1} + \right. \\
& \left. U \sum [C_{\text{Gene-Hexagon-Hexagon},l} \sin(\omega_{\text{Gene-Hexagon-Hexagon},l} t)]^{-1} \right] \left[1 + \right. \\
& \left. W \sum [L_{\text{virus-coil-I}} \sin(\omega_{\text{virus-coil-I}} t)] + T \sum [L_{\text{virus-coil-j}} \sin(\omega_{\text{virus-coil-j}} t)]^{-1} \right] \left[1 + \right. \\
& \left. Y [C_{\text{virus,Hexagon-pentagon},k} \sin(\omega_{\text{virus,Hexagon-pentagon},k} t)] + \right. \\
& \left. O \sum [C_{\text{virus,Hexagon-Hexagon},m} \sin(\omega_{\text{virus,Hexagon-Hexagon},m} t)] \right. \\
& \left. Z \sum [C_{\text{virus,Hexagon-pentagon},n} \sin(\omega_{\text{virus,Hexagon-pentagon},n} t)]^{-1} + \right. \\
& \left. X \sum [C_{\text{virus,Hexagon-Hexagon},m} \sin(\omega_{\text{virus,Hexagon-Hexagon},l} t)]^{-1} \right]^{-1/2} \quad (15)
\end{aligned}$$

Above frequency is different from initial genetic frequency which is a signature of new evolutions within a cell. This is because that before viral connections, the resonance frequency of gene-products was:

$$\Omega_{\text{gene-product}} \approx \left[\left[A \sum [L_{\text{Gene-coil-I}} \sin(\omega_{\text{Gene-coil-I}} t)] + B \sum [L_{\text{Gene-coil-j}} \sin(\omega_{\text{Gene-coil-j}} t)]^{-1} \right] \right. \\
\left. + 1 \right] \left[D \sum [C_{\text{Gene-Hexagon-pentagon},k} \sin(\omega_{\text{Gene-Hexagon-pentagon},k} t)] + \right.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& F \Sigma [C_{\text{Gene-Hexagon-Hexagon},m} \sin(\omega_{\text{Gene-Hexagon-Hexagon},m} t)] \\
& H \Sigma [C_{\text{Gene-Hexagon-pentagon},n} \sin(\omega_{\text{Gene-Hexagon-pentagon},n} t)]^{-1} + \\
& U \Sigma [C_{\text{Gene-Hexagon-Hexagon},l} \sin(\omega_{\text{Gene-Hexagon-Hexagon},l} t)]^{-1} [1 + \\
& ZX \Sigma [L_{\text{-product-coil-I}} \sin(\omega_{\text{virus-coil-I}} t)] + XZ [L_{\text{-product-coil-j}} \sin(\omega_{\text{virus-coil-j}} t)]^{-1}] [1 + \\
& S [C_{\text{-product,Hexagon-pentagon},k} \sin(\omega_{\text{-product,Hexagon-pentagon},k} t)] + \\
& M \Sigma [C_{\text{-product,Hexagon-Hexagon},m} \sin(\omega_{\text{-product,Hexagon-Hexagon},m} t)] \\
& J \Sigma [C_{\text{-product,Hexagon-pentagon},n} \sin(\omega_{\text{-product,Hexagon-pentagon},n} t)]^{-1} + \\
& I \Sigma [C_{\text{-product,Hexagon-Hexagon},m} \sin(\omega_{\text{-product,Hexagon-Hexagon},l} t)]^{-1}]^{-1/2} \quad (16)
\end{aligned}$$

Comparing two frequencies, one related to gene-virus system and another related to gene-products, we can consider the amount of decrease in correlating function for the correlation between genes and products:

$$\text{Correlating Function} \approx P_{\text{Corr}} \Omega_{\text{gene-product}} / [\Omega_{\text{gene-virus}}] \quad (17)$$

In figure 4, we show the correlating function for the correlation between genes and products in terms of time. It is clear that by connecting viruses, their waves cancel DNA waves and decrease their controls on products. In fact, new circuits are emerged which produce new products.

Figure 4. Correlating functions for DNA-products in terms of time.

Conclusion:

In this research, we have designed a method for induction of microbial vaccines by waves. In this method, DNAs and viruses are built from bases which join to each other and form capacitors, inductors and other elements of an electronic circuit. When a viral circuit become close to eye cells, its waves are detected and transmit to the brain. Then, neurons transmit these waves to cells and produce some currents in DNA circuits. These circuits produce some waves which move charges towards phosphors in phospholipids and other elements within a cell. Like a TV, By colliding charges and phosphors, some images are imaged. These images could be replicated by polymerases and some viruses are emerged. These viruses could be reversed transcribed and some new viral genes are emerged. These genes have their selves circuits and affect DNA circuits and their waves. Eventually, control of DNA on evolutions of a cell and its products decrease and some new products are

emerged. These evolutions cause that immune system response and number of T-cells increase. For this reason, we can use of this technique in building vaccines.

References:

- [1] Zhang L, Richards A, Barrasa MI, Hughes SH, Young RA, Jaenisch R. Reverse-transcribed SARS-CoV-2 RNA can integrate into the genome of cultured human cells and can be expressed in patient-derived tissues. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2021 May 25;118(21):e2105968118. doi: 10.1073/pnas.2105968118. PMID: 33958444.
- [2] Li YD, Chi WY, Su JH, Ferrall L, Hung CF, Wu TC. Coronavirus vaccine development: from SARS and MERS to COVID-19. *J Biomed Sci*. 2020 Dec 20;27(1):104. doi: 10.1186/s12929-020-00695-2. PMID: 33341119; PMCID: PMC7749790.
- [3] Dai L, Gao GF. Viral targets for vaccines against COVID-19. *Nat Rev Immunol*. 2021 Feb;21(2):73-82. doi: 10.1038/s41577-020-00480-0. Epub 2020 Dec 18. PMID: 33340022; PMCID: PMC7747004.
- [4] Nick K Jones et al., Screening of healthcare workers for SARS-CoV-2 highlights the role of asymptomatic carriage in COVID-19 transmission , *eLife* 2021;10:e68808 DOI: 10.7554/eLife.68808.
- [5] Baden LR, El Sahly HM, Essink B, et al. Efficacy and safety of the mRNA-1273 SARS-CoV-2 vaccine. *N Engl J Med* 2021;384:403-416.
- [6] Collier, D.A., De Marco, A., Ferreira, I.A.T.M. *et al.* Sensitivity of SARS-CoV-2 B.1.1.7 to mRNA vaccine-elicited antibodies. *Nature* 593, 136–141 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03412-7>.
- [7] Xie, X., Liu, Y., Liu, J. *et al.* Neutralization of SARS-CoV-2 spike 69/70 deletion, E484K and N501Y variants by BNT162b2 vaccine-elicited sera. *Nat Med* 27, 620–621 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-021-01270-4>.
- [8] Alexander Muik, Ann-Kathrin Wallisch, Bianca Sanger, Kena A. Swanson, Julia Muhl, Wei Chen, Hui Cai, Daniel Maurus, Ritu Sarkar, ozlem Tureci, Philip R. Dormitzer, Uğur Şahin, *Science* 12 Mar 2021: Vol. 371, Issue 6534, pp. 1152-1153
DOI: 10.1126/science.abg6105

[9] Levine-Tiefenbrun, M., Yelin, I., Katz, R. *et al.* Initial report of decreased SARS-CoV-2 viral load after inoculation with the BNT162b2 vaccine. *Nat Med* **27**, 790–792 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-021-01316-7>.

[10] Wilfredo F. Garcia-Beltran, Evan C. Lam, Kerri St. Denis, Adam D. Nitido, Zeidy H. Garcia, Blake M. Hauser, Jared Feldman, Maia N. Pavlovic, David J. Gregory, Mark C. Poznansky, Alex Sigal, Aaron G. Schmidt, A. John Iafrate, Vivek Naranbhai, Alejandro B. Balazs, Multiple SARS-CoV-2 variants escape neutralization by vaccine-induced humoral immunity, *Cell*, Volume 184, Issue 9, 2021, Pages 2372-2383.e9, ISSN 0092-8674, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2021.03.013>.

[11] Zhiwei Wu, Yaling Hu, Miao Xu, Zhen Chen, Wanqi Yang, Zhiwei Jiang, Minjie Li, Hui Jin, Guoliang Cui, Panpan Chen, Lei Wang, Guoqing Zhao, Yuzhu Ding, Yuliang Zhao, Weidong Yin, Safety, tolerability, and immunogenicity of an inactivated SARS-CoV-2 vaccine (CoronaVac) in healthy adults aged 60 years and older: a randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled, phase 1/2 clinical trial, *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*, 2021, ISSN 1473-3099, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099\(20\)30987-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(20)30987-7).

[12] Chadi M. Saad-Roy et al, Epidemiological and evolutionary considerations of SARS-CoV-2 vaccine dosing regimes, *Science*
Vol 372, Issue 6540
23 April 2021.

[13] Raches Ella, Krishna Mohan Vadrevu, Harsh Jogdand, Sai Prasad, Siddharth Reddy, Vamshi Sarangi, Brunda Ganneru, Gajanan Sapkal, Pragya Yadav, Priya Abraham, Samiran Panda, Nivedita Gupta, Prabhakar Reddy, Savita Verma, Sanjay Kumar Rai, Chandramani Singh, Sagar Vivek Redkar, Chandra Sekhar Gillurkar, Jitendra Singh Kushwaha, Satyajit Mohapatra, Venkat Rao, Randeep Guleria, Krishna Ella, Balram Bhargava, Safety and immunogenicity of an inactivated SARS-CoV-2 vaccine, BBV152: a double-blind, randomised, phase 1 trial, *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*, Volume 21, Issue 5, 2021, Pages 637-646, ISSN 1473-3099, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099\(20\)30942-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(20)30942-7).

[14] Shengli Xia, Yuntao Zhang, Yanxia Wang, Hui Wang, Yunkai Yang, George Fu Gao, Wenjie Tan, Guizhen Wu, Miao Xu, Zhiyong Lou, Weijin Huang, Wenbo Xu, Baoying Huang, Huijuan Wang, Wei Wang, Wei Zhang, Na Li, Zhiqiang Xie, Ling Ding, Wangyang You, Yuxiu Zhao, Xuqin Yang, Yang Liu, Qian Wang, Lili Huang, Yongli Yang, Guangxue Xu, Bojian Luo, Wenling Wang, Peipei Liu, Wanshen Guo, Xiaoming Yang, Safety and immunogenicity of an inactivated SARS-CoV-2 vaccine, BBIBP-CorV: a randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled, phase 1/2 trial, *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*, Volume 21, Issue 1, 2021, Pages 39-51, ISSN 1473-3099, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099\(20\)30831-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(20)30831-8).